

Using *OpenSimRoot* to model sweet potato root growth

Problem

Increasingly frequent and prolonged dry periods demand more drought-resilient crop genotypes or, in some regions, a shift toward alternative crops. Sweet potato is a promising future crop. However, storage root (tuber) development is economically critical and relies on carbon allocation processes, which are not yet well represented in existing plant models.

Solution

Sweet potato root and tuber development is simulated with *OpenSimRoot*, a software for functional-structural plant modelling in 3D soil.

Benefits

OpenSimRoot can simulate the development of storage roots in different environments. By providing a sweet-potato model input file, reproducible simulations and systematic experimentation on genotype performance, management strategies and environmental constraints are enabled, without the cost and time demands of field trials.

Practical application

The model is available upon request. This section focuses on defining key parameters for the required input file to set up a sweet potato model in *OpenSimRoot* (Figure 1); an applied example of model execution is provided in the barley model and interested users are encouraged to contact the modeling team for access and further guidance.

- **Root classes:** A transplanted cutting initially has nodal (1–2) and wound roots. These adventitious roots can thicken into storage roots near nodes or wound sites. Lateral roots, which are thicker and longer, can form second-order branches, and fine lateral roots arise from both adventitious and lateral roots.
- **Branching frequency:** Specify inter-branching distances for each lateral root class, e.g., define a log-normal distribution derived from WinRhizo (software) link analyses. Compare the lengths of the unbranched root tips among adventitious and lateral root classes. Define the number of nodal roots at transplanting and the timing and number of wound roots emerging thereafter.
- **Root elongation rates:** Provide class-specific root elongation rates (cm day^{-1}) as time series.
- **Angles:** Specify branching angles (in degrees relative to the parent roots' growth direction). Declare gravitropism for adventitious roots. Set the number of xylem poles for adventitious and lateral roots.
- **Root diameter:** Use scanned root images to assign class-specific diameters.
- **Secondary growth:** Enable secondary thickening for storage roots only (cm day^{-1} until a certain radius is reached).

Applicability box

Theme: Root modelling toolbox

Keywords: Sweet potato, root growth, functional-structural plant model (FSPM), root system architecture (RSA), simulation

Context: Simulations across regions and environments

Required time:

Data collection: from weeks to months (experiments and literature)

Installation: within minutes

Simulation: from minutes to hours

Equipment: Computer with *OpenSimRoot* and Paraview for visualisation

Software/hardware for data acquisition/analysis, e.g., RhizoVision Explorer or WinRhizo

- **Shoot system:** Specify the initial leaf area of the cutting (>0 cm²; four leaves). Note genotype-specific differences in leaf area.
- **Biomass allocation:** Set the specific root volume (in g cm⁻³ or cm³ g⁻¹) to ensure total biomass aligns with the root system length.
- **Carbon fixation:** Set the light use efficiency (LUE) such that the biomass is correctly simulated. Specify respiration and carbon exudation rates.
- **Nutrients uptake:** Apply Michaelis–Menten uptake parameters.
- **Environmental inputs:** OpenSimRoot can use site-specific environment data, e.g., data from weather stations. For soil, define hydraulic parameters (van Genuchten curve), initial hydraulic heads (or volumetric water content), compare with water table. Set nutrient levels, C/N ratio and/or mineralisation.

Figure 1: Visualisation of a 50-day old Beauregard sweet potato root system. False colours show the nitrate concentration in the soil solution (red to blue over grey). The cutting is shown in green, three storage roots in red and all other root classes in white. This simulation consists of:

1) the structural plant model (roots, leaf area, ontology); 2) dry mass (derived from the structure); 3) photosynthesis (Beer's law & LUE); 4) carbon allocation (structure, respiration, exudation, starch production); 5) evapotranspiration (Penman-Monteith), water uptake and xylem transport (Ohm's law analogy) 6) uptake and allocation of N, P, K; 7) water and nutrient transport in the soil (Richard's equation and solute transport: advection, diffusion & sorption); 8) plant physiological and plasticity responses to various queues.

Further information

- Root2Res. (2025) Using OpenSimRoot to simulate barley root growth to identify stress-resilient traits. <https://zenodo.org/records/17738404>
- Root2Res. (2025) Using OpenSimRoot to model faba bean root growth. <https://zenodo.org/records/17738382>
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- Postma J.A. & Black K. (2020) CH02 - Advances in root architectural modeling during the last decade. In *Understanding and improving crop root function. Advances in modelling plant root systems*, p. 34. Burleigh Dodds Science Publishing, UK. <http://dx.doi.org/10.19103/AS.2020.0075.02>
- Schäfer, E.D., Owen, M.R., Postma, J.A., Kuppe, C., Black, C.K., Lynch, J.P. (2022). Simulating Crop Root Systems Using OpenSimRoot. In: Lucas, M. (eds) *Plant Systems Biology. Methods in Molecular Biology*, vol 2395. Humana, New York, NY. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-1816-5_15
- OpenSimRoot weblink: <https://rootmodels.gitlab.io/>

About this practice abstract and Root2Resilience

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Root2Resilience: The project is running from September 2022 to August 2027. The overall goal of Root2Resilience – Root phenotyping and genetic improvement for rotational crops resilient to environmental change – is to develop root phenotyping, genetic and modelling tools and use them to define and test innovative genotype ideotypes able to enhance the tolerance to abiotic stress and carbon sequestration in soils.

Project website: root2res.eu

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